

ESP INSTRUCTION: OVERCOMING CHALLENGES IN MATERIAL DEVELOPMENT AND SUBJECT KNOWLEDGE ACQUISITION

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***Abstract:** This article examines the key challenges faced by teachers of English for Specific Purposes (ESP), including insufficient subject knowledge, inadequate needs analysis, and difficulties in developing or adapting suitable materials. It emphasizes the importance of tailoring ESP courses to learners' specific professional and linguistic needs, achieved through comprehensive needs analysis and collaboration with subject-matter experts. The article also explores strategies for addressing the challenges of heterogeneous classes, where diverse learner backgrounds necessitate flexible and innovative teaching approaches.*

***Key words:** ESP, challenges, course design, carrier content, real content, needs analysis, special field knowledge, heterogeneous classes.*

Introduction

English for Specific Purposes (ESP) is a learner-centered approach to language teaching that prioritizes the specific needs of the learners [Hutchinson & Waters, 1996]. ESP courses are designed to cater to these particular requirements by equipping students with the language skills necessary for communication within their respective professional domains.

Research on the difficulties faced by ESP instructors when designing or delivering courses remains limited. Teaching ESP often involves specialized language that may even challenge native English speakers [Widdowson.1998]. For instance, teaching English for Legal Purposes (ELP) or Business requires domain-specific expertise. Additionally, ESP instructors may grapple with whether their role involves teaching English for a specific field, such as Law or Business English, or teaching the field's content using English as a medium.

Main part. According to Robinson [1991], a foundational element of an ESP

course is a Needs Analysis (NA), which identifies the specific tasks learners must perform using English. NA involves gathering information about learners' goals, expectations, deficiencies, and requirements to tailor the course accordingly. This approach is regarded as central to ESP, as the curriculum is developed based on a comprehensive understanding of learners' needs.

One common challenge for ESP teachers is insufficient knowledge about the purposes for which learners require English, often linked to inadequate needs analyses. Hutchinson and Waters emphasize that ESP differs from General English by focusing on learner awareness of these specific needs. This awareness influences what is deemed relevant and appropriate in a language course. As noted by Dudley-Evans and St. John [1998], needs analysis serves as the foundation of ESP course design, enabling instructors to adapt their teaching strategies. Information for NA can be sourced from learners, educators, industry professionals, literature, or subject-matter experts. In conducting an NA, practitioners may not only inquire about learners' objectives but also observe the contexts in which they will use English.

Many educators cite the scarcity of suitable materials as a major obstacle in ESP course design [Williams, 2014]. While materials are a critical component of all English courses, determining their relevance and application poses a unique challenge in ESP. In contexts where English functions as a foreign language, course materials may be the primary source of exposure to the language. Consequently, additional resources should be provided to enhance learners' engagement with English.

ESP materials must authentically reflect the language used in real-life contexts. When ready-made materials fail to align with learners' needs, instructors often develop their own resources. Although ESP teachers are not typically material developers, Dudley-Evans and St. John [1998] describe them as material providers who adapt and modify existing resources to suit learners' specific requirements. For example, if no available textbook aligns with the needs of a

particular group, the instructor may revise existing materials to create a more relevant and customized learning experience.

Since ESP instructors are typically not experts in the learners' professional fields, they may find the subject matter unfamiliar, leading to challenges when teaching complex texts. This makes it imperative for ESP teachers to acquire some knowledge of both the content and its context. For instance, an instructor teaching English to law students should possess at least a basic understanding of legal concepts. Such knowledge enables the teacher to facilitate authentic communication and classroom activities, as learners are already familiar with the carrier content. This understanding can be developed by reading relevant literature, subscribing to professional journals, keeping up with current studies, observing subject-specific classes, or consulting with subject-matter experts.

In courses where students begin studying ESP from their first year, the teacher must address not only the learners' language proficiency but also their professional competence. Variability in learners' strengths—some excelling in English, others in content knowledge – can complicate the course design process. To address this, instructors might consider assigning tailored tasks to individual students. For example, students lacking content knowledge could be encouraged to engage with field-specific literature to improve their understanding.

Teaching ESP to heterogeneous classes, where learners come from different disciplines, professions, or management levels, adds another layer of complexity. It can be challenging to find materials, textbooks, and activities that are universally relevant to a diverse group. Even adapting existing resources may prove difficult in such contexts [Panferova, 2019]. For instance, learners from the same organization might represent varying management levels, such as secretaries and managers, requiring different approaches. Conversely, homogeneous classes allow for more focused material development, as learners typically share a common professional background.

Conclusion. The demanding nature of ESP courses presents numerous

challenges for instructors. These include limited field-specific knowledge, inadequate needs analysis, difficulties in sourcing appropriate materials, and lack of administrative support. To mitigate these issues, ESP practitioners should begin with a comprehensive needs analysis and design course materials that align closely with learners' needs and expectations.

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